

CLINICAL PSYCHOLOGY TERMINOLOGY FROM A TRANSLATION PERSPECTIVE

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The purpose of this work is to investigate the field of clinical psychology, which has been an important and long-standing field throughout the evolution of human knowledge, and yet still contains many mysteries and questions that remain to be answered in the future.

The study provides general characteristics alongside specific peculiarities; it also comprises a linguistic and terminological analysis of the field from a translation perspective that is bound to improve not only the professional knowledge and abilities, but also bring forth valuable information about human interaction, and offer solutions to day to day problems.

In order to render this type of specialized language texts, translators must attempt to identify the translation difficulties that clinical psychology terminology could pose, go beyond correspondences at the level of individual terms and be able to establish interlinguistic references to entire knowledge structures, and more important, the problems the translators of the source text face and the way they overcome them.

As a result of the carried out research it allows us to realize that clinical psychology terminology is particularly dynamic and it requires responsibility from both: the psychologist and the translator, ability to concentrate as well as thoroughness and accuracy that can be used in the process of the source text translation into the target text.

Keywords: *terminology, clinical psychology, term formation, semantic relations, difficulties of translation, source language, target language, origin, monosemy.*

DESPRE TERMINOLOGIA DOMENIULUI PSIHOLOGIEI CLINICE DIN PERSPECTIVA TRADUCERII

Scopul acestei cercetări este studierea domeniului psihologiei clinice, fiind unul deosebit de important de-a lungul evoluției cunoașterii umane, dar, care conține încă multe mistere și provocări și așteaptă soluții.

Studiul oferă atât caracteristici generale, cât și particularități specifice, propune o analiză lingvistică și terminologică a domeniului din perspectiva traducerii, care are drept obiectiv îmbunătățirea cunoștințelor și abilităților profesionale, oferă informații valoroase despre interacțiunea umană dar și răspunsuri la întrebările existente.

Traducerea textor lingvistice specializate este identificarea dificultăților, depistarea corespondențelor la nivel de termen și stabilirea referințelor interlingvistice ale structurilor terminologice din domeniu, care sunt doar unele din problemele cu care se confruntă traducătorii textului sursă și modalitatea cu care acestea sunt depășite.

Ca rezultat al cercetării efectuate conchidem că terminologia psihologiei clinice este deosebit de dinamică și necesită responsabilitate atât din partea psihologului, cât și a traducătorului, capacitate de concentrare, precum minuțiozitate și acuratețe în traducerea textului sursă în textul țintă.

Cuvinte-cheie: *terminologie, psihologie clinică, modalități de formare a termenilor, relații semantice, dificultăți de traducere, limba sursă, limba țintă, origine, aspect monosemantic.*

Introduction

Terminology is a fairly new branch of linguistics, as it has been systematically developed only in recent decades. Various definitions have been proposed for this field, as some linguists consider it to be a separate scientific discipline with its own theory, despite borrowing some concepts from other fields, while others believe it to be a set of practices that are meant to deal with social needs, optimizing communication among specialists. Thus, according to J. Sager [1, p. 2], terminology is the study and the field of activity concerned with the creation, collection,

description, processing, and presentation of terms belonging to a specialized area of usage of one or more languages, providing a pragmatic and applied view of this field. He denies the fact that terminology is a separate discipline, mentioning that it is characterized by a number of practices, but acknowledges that the field has theoretical foundations on which these practices are based. On the other hand, Teresa Cabré [2, p. 14] states that terminology is a discipline that is concerned with the study and compilation of specialized terms, adding that not all experts agree that terminology constitutes a separate discipline, nor do all consider it a theoretical subject. T. Cabré [2, p. 162] adds that users of terminology, who range from specialists in various fields to language professionals such as terminologists, technical writers, translators and interpreters.

As mentioned above, terminology and clinical psychology, separate scientific disciplines are two fields that develop along with human progress and knowledge in these fields constantly needs to be updated. It is only natural that clinical psychology terminology would offer complex challenges to clinical psychology practitioners, terminologists, and linguists in the same extent. Consequently, translators of clinical psychology are also not exempt from the various difficulties that go hand in hand with this specialized field and it is namely terminology and the work of terminologists that helps translators in their own professional endeavor. Although psychology itself is considered an old enough domain, new theories and approaches are being developed year by year, and consequently, translators are constantly faced with new challenges, and making decisions that can play a part in the mental and emotional wellbeing of people all around the world, and even the very course of their lives.

Source of examples

For this study, we have decided to observe how English clinical psychology terms are translated into Romanian in a modern approach to clinical psychology, and namely Transactional Analysis, which was developed by Eric Berne in 1957 [3]. We decided to choose the book “TA Today: A New Introduction to Transactional Analysis” by Ian Stewart and Vann Joines [4], and its translation “AT astăzi: o nouă introducere în analiza tranzacțională”, which translation was carried out by Constantin Chevereșan and Luminița Chevereșan [5], due to its highly regarded status in this field, and the fact that it is used both as methodological material in universities around the world, but that it is also intended for personal use, regardless of specialization. Thus, we intend to analyze the clinical psychology terms from various points of view, finding new evidence with regard to clinical psychology terminology and clinical psychology translation.

Results and Discussions

Before delving into our analysis of the book “TA Today: A New Introduction to Transactional Analysis” by Ian Stewart and Vann Joines [4] and its translation “AT astăzi: o nouă introducere în analiza tranzacțională” [5], we would list and describe a number of translation techniques proposed by the two well-known theorists, Jean-Paul Vinay and Jean Darbelnet [6], when referring to other authors’ contributions to this topic, P. Newmark [7] being a notable example, provide a number of practical examples and comment on the frequency of use in terminology as a whole, provide a multifaceted linguistic analysis of the identified translated terms in Romanian and attempt to identify the translation difficulties that clinical psychology terminology could pose, and more importantly, the problems the translators of the source text have faced and how they have overcome them.

Jean-Paul Vinay and Jean Darbelnet [6, p.111], two prominent representatives of the French School of Comparative Stylistics, their pioneer work “*Stylistique comparée du français et de l’anglais*”, published in 1958, provided the first classification of translation techniques and had a clear methodological purpose. This classification was divided into two different methods of translation, direct and oblique, which included seven translation techniques in total, and is still widely used today. The direct translation techniques include *borrowing*, *calque* and *literal translation*, while the indirect ones, also called oblique, include *transposition*, *modulation*, *equivalence* and *adaptation*.

In addition to these seven translation techniques, Vinay and Darbelnet [6, p. 205] proposed some other complementary techniques, most of which come in opposing pairs. But we should emphasize that while all of the aforementioned translation techniques can be used when rendering general language units of translation, only several can be chosen to render specialized language, and namely, terminological units. This is explained by the fact that specialized communication implies a high level of correspondence between the source and the target texts, and a consistency in term usage within the target language. Thus, only a number of translation techniques can be chosen to render terminological units from one language into another.

Let us start with the translation technique known as *equivalence*, also known as established equivalence or recognized translation, which consists of using a term or expression recognized by dictionaries or language in use as an equivalent in the target language. Due to the fact that terminology is very precise and does not allow ambiguity in translation, many terms are translated through this technique, as we can observe in the following examples from the book “TA Today”. First we can analyze the term *activity*, which has been selected from the following context: “*The Adult is the predominant ego-state in activity*” [4, p. 91], translated into Romanian as “*În activitate, starea predominantă a eului este Adultul*” [5, p. 73]. The origin of this term comes from Old French, *activité*, which was in turn taken from the Medieval Latin *activitatem*, based on the Latin *activus*, meaning “active”, being first attested in the English language circa 1400, with the meaning “active or secular life”, while its meanings of “state of being active”, “capacity for acting on matter”, and of “an educational exercise” have been recorded in the 1520s, 1540s, and the 1920s respectively. It should be noted that while term belongs field of clinical psychology, and the subfield of Transactional Analysis, it has been created through the term formation method of *terminologization*, and thus also has a general language meaning. Thus, its specialized definition is a mode of time-structuring in which those concerned have the objective of achieving an overtly agreed goal, as opposed to merely talking about it [4, p. 326], its general language meaning is a thing that a person or group does or has done [8]. We should also mention that this term appears in the field of chemistry, and is defined as a thermodynamic quantity representing the effective concentration of a particular component in a solution or other system, equal to its concentration multiplied by an activity coefficient [8]. The Romanian version of the clinical psychology term is *activitate*, which was introduced into the language from the French *activité*, naturally, having been based on the same Old French origin as its English counterpart. Thus, both the English and the Romanian forms are similar, and can be easily translated even without the help of a specialized dictionary.

Let us carry on with more other terms, such as *game*, identified within “*The analysis of games is a major part of TA theory*” [4, p. 92], a context translated as “*Analiza jocurilor este o parte importantă a teoriei AT*” [5, p. 73]. It has been attested since the 1200s, and has its origin in the Old English *gamen*, which means “joy, fun, game”, which was based on the Proto-Germanic collective

prefix *ga-* and the root *mann*, “person”, creating the meaning of “people together”. The term can be defined as a series of transactions with a Con, a Gimmick, a Switch, and a Crossup, leading to a Payoff, which is Eric Berne’s definition, and a more explicit definition given by Joines: the process of doing something with an ulterior motive that is outside of Adult awareness, does not become explicit until the participants switch the way they are behaving, and results in everyone feeling confused, misunderstood, and wanting to blame the other person [4, p. 329]. As it was created through the method of *terminologization*, it has a general language meaning, and namely an activity that one engages in for amusement or fun [8], which is an ironic choice when we compare it to the terminological meaning proposed by Transactional Analysis theorists. It was translated through the Romanian equivalent *joc*, while in our context it is in its inflected plural genitive form, which entered the language by adapting the Latin *jocus*, and is used in our context in its inflected plural genitive form. The translation of this term should not pose any problems to a translator.

A term which also requires analysis is *gimmick*, found in “*A game is a series of ulterior transactions with a gimmick, leading to a usually well-concealed but well-defined payoff*” [4, p. 242], a sentence translated into Romanian as “*Un joc este o serie de tranzacții ulterioare cu o Stratagemă, decând spre un Beneficiu negativ adesea bine ascuns, dar și bine definit*” [5, p. 172]. The origin of this term is quite uncertain; it has been attested since the 1910s, predominantly in the United States, and is perhaps an alteration of *gimcrack*, which is a showy object of little use or value [8]. In the subfield of Transactional Analysis, the *gimmick* is a transactional response which on the psychological level conveys that the person has accepted an invitation into game-playing [4, p. 330]. However, as it is a term created through *terminologization*, it has a general language meaning, which is a trick or device intended to attract attention, publicity, or trade [8]. The Romanian version of the term is *stratagemă*, which in the general language denotes a “trick”, and has its origin in the French *stratagème*, making the translation somewhat challenging, which can be eased by using a specialized dictionary, or a glossary.

Another term worth analyzing is *Martian*, extracted from the context “*His 'Martian' signals simply: 'And I'm glad to see you all here'*” [4, p. 180], which has been translated as “*'Marțianul' lui semnalizează pur și simplu 'Și mă bucur să vă văd pe toți aici'*” [5, p. 131]. It was first attested in the late 14th century and was originally used in reference to astrological influence; it was created based on the Latin *Martius*, “sacred to Mars” referring to the god of war. In the subfield of Transactional Analysis *Martian* is defined as an interpretation of human behavior and communication which entails observation without preconceptions [4, p. 331], and had the general language meaning of something relating to the planet Mars or its supposed inhabitants, or a hypothetical or fictional inhabitant of Mars [8]. This term as well has been created through *terminologization* by Eric Berne, and is often found in set phrases such as *Martian thinking*, or *Martian messages*. This particular general language unit was chosen due to popular culture, as in science-fiction movies and books, aliens from Mars or other planets that come in contact with human beings are generally described as detached from our cultural and emotional behavior, analyzing us like scientists in a lab. The Romanian term *Marțianul*, is an inflected nominative form of the basic unit *Marțian*, and has its origin in the French *martien*, which was also based on the same Latin origin. The term is not used in other fields or subfields, and can be easily translated due to the similarity between the source and target language origins.

The last example of equivalence refers to the translation of the term *vector* within the following context: “*Thus the vector ends up at the Adult on your diagram*”, [4, p. 59] translated as “*Deci vectorul ajunge în Adultul din diagrama ta*” [5, p. 51]. This term is a noun of Latin origin,

vector, attested since 1704, having the meaning “line joining a fixed point and a variable point”, later obtaining the meaning of “quantity having magnitude and direction”. In clinical psychology it denotes an arrow on a transactional diagram connecting the ego-state from which a communication is issued to the ego-state to which it is addressed [4, p. 335]. It was created through transdisciplinary borrowing, as its primary meaning is in the field of physics and mathematics, and it denotes a quantity having direction as well as magnitude, especially as determining the position of one point in space relative to another [8]. Based on this definition, other fields also borrowed and incorporated this term, such as computing, genetics, and biology. While in the general language such a trait is named polysemy, in terminology it is often considered to be an example of homonymy. When it comes to the Romanian version, the term is used in its inflected form, and was borrowed and adapted from the French *vecteur*. Consequently, translating this term is not a problem, even for an unspecialized speaker.

Another technique that was prevalent is the translation of clinical psychology terms is **transposition**, which is characterized by the change of a grammatical category, but also occurs when the location of various parts of speech within a sentence are switched based on the particular language. The following are some analyzed terms that have been translated with this technique. To start with we can take the nominal phrase *Adapted Child* from the following context: “*When I do so, I am said to be in the Adapted Child part of my Child ego-state*” [4, p. 22], translated as “*Când procedez astfel, spunem că mă aflu în partea de Copil Adaptat a stării de Copil a eului meu*” [5, p. 26]. The term is formed from the adjective *adapted*, which has its origin in the Old French *adapter*, from the Latin *adaptare*, “to fit, adjust”, and the noun *child*, based on the Old English *cild*, which was formed from the Proto-Germanic *kiltham*, meaning “fetus, infant, newly born person”. It is defined as a subdivision of the Child in the functional model, indicating how the individual may use this ego-state in conforming to rules or societal demands [4, p. 326]. It is predominantly used in the subfield of Transactional Analysis, and can be encountered in more complex set phrases such as *Negative Adapted Child* or *Positive Adapted Child*. The Romanian term is a transposed translation of the source one, *Copil* being a noun of Albanian origin, *kopilë*, and the adjective *adaptat*, which is a derivation of the verb *a adapta*, from the French *adapter*, and Latin *adaptare*. In translation, the word order is switched, which corresponds to the definition of transposition.

With regard to the term *Adult ego-state*, it was selected from the context “*You know that when I am in my Adult ego-state, I am responding to the here-and-now with all the resources available to me as a grown-up*” [4, p. 19], which has been translated as “*Știți că atunci când sunt în starea de Adult a eului, reacționez la aici-și-acum cu toate resursele de care dispun ca persoană matură*” [5, p. 24]. This term was formed by combining the noun *adult*, which functions as a modifier in our term, from Latin *adultus*, attested since the 1530s, meaning “grown, mature”, and the compound hyphenated term *ego-state*, the noun *ego* having been attested since 1714 as a term in metaphysics with the meaning “the self”, borrowed from the Latin *ego*, “I”, and the noun *state*, attested since the 1200s, was based on the Old French *estat*, and Latin *status*, meaning “position, condition”. It is defined as a set of behaviors, thoughts and feelings which are direct responses to the here-and-now, not copied from parents or parent-figures nor replayed from the individual's own childhood [4, p. 326]. The term can be used in other forms, such as *Child ego-state* or *Parent ego-state*, or can be simply shortened to the term *Adult*. The unit is always capitalized when used in its terminological meaning, in order to avoid confusion with the general language unit. The Romanian term includes the inflected noun *starea*, a derivation of the verb *a sta*, based on the Latin *stare*, the preposition *de*, based on the Latin *de*, the noun *adult*, based on the French *adulte*, originally from

Latin, *adultus*, the preposition *a*, from French *à*, and Latin *ad*, and finally the inflected noun *eului*, which was based on the Latin *ego* as well. Once again, there is a shift in word order, meaning that the technique used to translate the source term was transposition.

On the other hand, the term *behavioral diagnosis* has been identified in the following context: “Now you have consistent clues from expression and voice tone which help confirm your behavioral diagnosis of Adult” [4, p. 39], which has been translated as “Acum ai niște indicii concordante ale expresiei și tonului vocii, care te ajută la confirmarea diagnosticului comportamental de Adult” [5, p. 39]. While *behavioral* is an adjective attested in psychology since 1927, from the noun *behavior*, the verb *to behave*, “conduct, comport”, and the adjective forming suffix *-al*, and the noun *diagnosis*, attested since 1680, being a Latin application of the Greek *diagnosis*, “a discerning, distinguishing”. The term is part of the clinical psychology field, being used in various of its subfields, but in the subfield of Transactional Analysis is defined as judgment of which ego-state an individual is in by observation of that individual's behavior [4, p. 327], and has no synonyms or additional meanings, being translated by the inflected genitive noun *diagnosticului*, with the base *diagnostic*, borrowed from the French *diagnostic*, and the adjective *comportamental*, based on the French *comportemental*, which has a similar meaning.

Finally, let us analyze the phrasal unit *winning script*, as found in: “The child who chooses 'I'm OK, you're OK' is likely to build a winning script” [4, p.117], which has been translated as “Copilul care alege 'Eu sunt OK, tu ești OK' își va construi probabil un scenariu câștigător” [5, p. 90]. The term is based on the participle *winning*, from the verb *to win*, meaning “to be victorious”, attested since the 1300s, it is a fusion of the Old English *winnan* “to labor, toil” and *gewinnan* “conquer, obtain”, and the noun *script*, based on the Old French *escrit*, a “piece of writing”, and the Latin *scriptum*, “a writing, a line”. It is defined as a script in which the payoff is happy or fulfilling, and/or entails success in accomplishing a declared purpose [4, p. 335]. It does not have any other meanings or synonyms, and we can include it into the subfield of Transactional Analysis. In translation, the Romanian noun *scenariu* is used, which we have often encountered in our analysis, and the adjective *câștigător*, created through derivation, by adding the suffix *-ător*, to the root *câștiga*, from the verb *a câștiga*, based on the Latin *castigare*. Rendering this term should not pose any problems as the elements themselves are not highly specialized and only need to be positioned correctly according to grammar conventions.

Another translation technique for which we have identified some examples is **literal translation**, which is one-for-one translation. Let us start with the analysis of the term *Adult in the Child* which was selected from the following context: “Their work is necessary reading if you want thorough understanding of the Adult in the Child” [4, p. 35], translated as “Este important să citim lucrările lor dacă dorim o înțelegere aprofundată a Adultului din Copil” [5, p. 36]. The term is formed from the noun *adult*, which functions as a modifier in our term, from Latin *adultus*, attested since the 1530s, meaning “grown, mature”, the preposition *in*, the definite article *the*, and the noun *child*, based on the Old English *cild*, which was formed from the Proto-Germanic *kiltham*, meaning “fetus, infant, newly born person”. It is defined as part of the second-order structure of the Child, representing the young child's strategies for reality-testing and problem-solving [4, p. 326], and is predominantly used in the subfield of Transactional Analysis. The Romanian term is a unit-for-unit translation of the source one, *adultului* being an inflected noun of French origin, *adulte*, originally from Latin, *adultus*, the preposition *din*, and the noun *copil*, a noun of Albanian origin, *kopilī*, the structure and order of the terminological elements remaining the same.

A similar example is *Child in the Child*, which was found in the context “*These will form the bulk of the memories stored in the Child in the Child*” [4, p. 35], which has been translated as “*Aceasta va forma majoritatea amintirilor stocate în Copilul din Copil*” [5, p. 36]. This term was formed similarly to the term above, containing only the Old English *cild*, the preposition *in*, and the definite article *the*. It is defined as part of the second-order structure of the Child, representing stored memories of experiences from earlier stages of the child's own development [4, p. 327]. The Romanian version contains the inflected *copilul*, the preposition *din*, and the base noun *copil*. As we can see, in the translation of both terms, the unit order remains the same, and each unit is rendered literally.

And lastly, we can take a look at the term *third rule of communication*, extracted from the following context, which was selected from the context “*Recall Berne’s Third Rule of Communication: when transactions are ulterior, the significant message is on the psychological level*” [4, p. 126], and has been translated as “*Amintiți-vă cea de-a 3-a Regulă a Comunicării a lui Berne: atunci când tranzacțiile sunt ulterioare, mesajul semnificativ e la nivel psihologic*” [5, p. 96]. Once again, the term resembles the other two above, but includes the adjective *third*, based on the Old English *þridda*, from Proto-Germanic *þridja*. It denotes that the behavioral outcome of an ulterior transaction is determined at the psychological and not at the social level [4 p. 325]. As with the other two, the term is mostly used in the subfield of Transactional Analysis, and the Romanian term includes the same elements as above, with the exception of the numeral *a treia*, which is written in its Roman numeral form, and is of Latin origin, *tres*. Once again, each element was translated one-for-one, meaning that the technique used to translate the source term was literal translation.

Now we can move on to talk about *borrowings* in the translation of clinical psychology terms, borrowing implying a translation technique through which a source language unit is incorporated into the target language. For example, we have the term *cathexis*, which was selected from the context “*Berne followed Freud in hypothesizing the concept of psychic energy, or cathexis*” [4, p. 48], which has been translated as “*Berne s-a inspirat de la Freud când a creat ipoteza conceptului de energie psihică sau cathexis*” [5, p. 45]. This term was first attested in 1922, and is a Latinized form of Greek *kathexis* “holding, retention”. It is defined as a theoretical construct representing psychic energy, postulated by Berne to explain shifts between ego-states; or it can denote a name of institute founded by the Schiffs and of the 'school' of TA which uses their approach [4, p. 327]. The term is used not only in Transactional Analysis, but also in general psychoanalysis as well. The Romanian term is identical to the source language one, as it is a pure borrowing, without any adaptation to the target language.

Let us carry on by briefly analyzing the term *driver*, which appears in the following context: “*The name 'driver' is used because the child feels a compulsion to follow these commands*” [4, p. 131], and was translated into Romanian as “*Numele de “driver” se folosește deoarece copilul simte o constrângere de a asculta de aceste comenzi*” [5, p. 100]. It is based on the noun *driver*, which has its origin in the Old English *drifan* “to pursue; rush against”, from Proto-Germanic *driban*. Thus, it denotes one of five distinctive behavioral sequences, played out over a time-period between half-a-second and a few seconds, which are the functional manifestations of negative counterscripts [4, p. 328]. It should not be confused with its general language meaning of a person who drives a vehicle, or with its specialized meaning of a computer program that makes it possible for a computer to use other pieces of equipment [8], as they are different concepts found within separate

fields. The Romanian translation is identical to the source language version, making it easy to render.

On the other hand, the term *racket* has been identified in the following context: “*We shall meet this idea again when we discuss games, rackets and script*” [4, p. 74], which has been translated as “*Vom reveni la această idee când vom discuta despre jocuri, racket-uri și scenarii*” [5, p. 61]. It has been attested since the 1560s with the meaning “a loud noise”, often compared to the Gaelic *racaid*, meaning “noise”. The term is mostly used in the subfield of Transactional Analysis, with the meaning of scripty behaviors, intended outside awareness as a means of manipulating the environment, and entailing the person's experiencing a racket feeling [4, p. 332]. It was formed through terminologization, as in the general language it denotes a loud unpleasant noise, a bat used especially in tennis, and an illegal or dishonest scheme for obtaining money [8], but has no additional terminological meanings or partial synonyms, and was borrowed into Romanian due to the lack of a more appropriate unit.

The next technique worth presenting is *half-calque*, which implies borrowing half of a designation and translating the other one. The following are some analyzed examples of identified half-calques that belong to clinical psychology terminology. First, let us analyze the term *negative stroke*, selected from “*To satisfy our stimulus-hunger, we can use negative strokes just as readily as positives*” [4, p. 73], translated as “*Pentru a ne satisface foamea de stimulare putem folosi și stroke-uri negative, ca și pe cele pozitive*” [5, p. 61]. The term is formed from the adjective *negative*, attested since 1400, with the meaning of “expressing denial”, being of Old French origin, *negatif*, or directly from Latin *negatives*, and the noun *stroke* which we have analyzed above, used in its plural form. It is defined as a stroke which the receiver experiences as unpleasant [4, p. 331]. It is predominantly used in the subfield of Transactional Analysis, and is translated by borrowing the term *stroke* into Romanian, and inflecting it according to its grammar conventions to a plural form, and translating the adjective *negative*, which in the target language is again inflected, *negative*, from the base form *negativ*, having its origin in the French *negatif*, and Latin *negativus*. Its opposite is the term *positive stroke*, which was found in the context: “*In our opening example, you and your neighbor exchanged positive strokes*” [4, p. 73], having the following translation “*În exemplul nostru inițial, tu și vecinul ați schimbat stroke-uri pozitive*” [5, p. 61]. The term consists of the adjective *positive*, from Old French *positif* and directly from Latin *positives*, meaning “settled by agreement”, and the term *stroke*. It can be defined as a stroke which the receiver experiences as pleasant [4, p. 332]. The Romanian version consists of the plural form of the borrowed term *stroke*, and the plural adjective *pozitive* similarly to the previous example. In both cases the order of the two units is switched in the target language version.

Another example of a *half-calque* is the term *stroking profile*, from “*Jim McKenna has devised a diagram which he calls the stroking profile*” [4, p. 81], which sounds in Romanian as “*Jim McKenna a creat un grafic pe care-l numește profil de stroking*” [5, p. 66]. The term was formed by adjoining the participle of the term *stroke*, and namely *stroking*, and the noun *profile*, attested since the 1650s, meaning “a drawing of the outline” from the Italian *profilo*. It is defined as a bar-chart diagram to analyze an individual's preference for giving, taking, asking for and refusing to give strokes [4, p. 334], and is only used in the context of Transactional Analysis and clinical psychology. The Romanian version consists of the noun *profil*, a borrowing of the French *profil*, and the borrowed English term *stroking*, including the preposition *de*, to make a transposition possible in translation.

Further on, we can discuss the technique called **expansion**, which is also called amplification, and implies rendering a term with more signifiers than the source term contains. Here is a first example: *allower*, extracted from the context “*If you were lucky with your parents, you got some of these allowers from them*” [4, p. 163], which has been translated as “*Daca ai fost norocos în privința părinților, ai primit poate asemenea mesaje permisive de la ei*” [5, p. 121]. The term contains the unit *allower*, a derived version of the verb to allow, attested since the 14th century, having its origin in the Middle English *allowen*, “to praise, approve of”, from the Anglo-French *alouer*, Old French *aloer*, and finally, from Latin *allocare*. The term is defined as the positive converse of a driver [4, p. 326]. It can be used in its general language meaning of a person who allows something, making it a term created through terminologization. It does not have any additional specialized meanings or synonyms, and can be included into the subfield of Transactional Analysis. It is translated through the plural noun *mesaje*, which is of French origin, *message*, and the adjective *permissive*, also from French *permissif*, thus adding another element to the target language term in order to avoid any confusion, and to make the term sound natural.

As for the term *pastime*, it appears in the context: “*But the content of a pastime is not programmed so strictly as that of a ritual*” [4, p. 89], translated into Romanian as “*Dar conținutul unor discuții pentru petrecerea timpului nu e atât de strict programat ca cel al unui ritual*” [5, p. 72]. The term includes the compound noun *pastime*, attested since the 15th century, having its origin in the Middle English *passee tyme*, meaning “recreation”, formed on the model of Middle French *passee-temps*. It denotes a mode of time-structuring in which people talk about a subject but have no intention of taking action concerning it [4, p. 332], belonging to the subfield of Transactional Analysis and is mostly used within it. However, it can also be used as a general language unit, denoting an activity that someone does regularly for enjoyment rather than work [8], thus being a term created through terminologization. The Romanian version is quite longer, including the plural noun *discuții*, which is of French origin, *discussion*, the preposition *de*, the inflected noun *petrecerea*, from the verb *a petrece*, from Latin *petraicere*, and finally, inflected noun *timpului*, from *timp*, based on the Latin *tempus*. In this case, the translator chose to render the term by explaining it in short, rather than finding an appropriate equivalent.

And finally, we can speak about **modulation**, which is very rarely encountered in specialized translation, but can be used if the situation calls for it. It involves changing the form of the message through a recasting of semantic perspective, and one example, and possibly the single one within the extracted terminological corpus, is the term *marshmallow-throwing*, which was found in the context: “*Eric Berne described this as marshmallow-throwing*” [4, p. 75], having the following translation “*Eric Berne a descris această situație cu numele de dulcegării nesincere*” [5, p. 62]. The term consists of the noun *marshmallow*, which has its origin in the Old English *mersc-mealwe*, meaning a “kind of mallow plant which grows near salt marshes”, and the gerund *throwing*, from the verb *to throw*, attested since the 1300s, from Old English *þrawan* “to twist, turn”, from Proto-Germanic *throw*. It can be defined as giving out insincere positive strokes [4, p. 331]. We can include the term in the subfield of Transactional Analysis, as it is mostly used within its confines, without appearing in any other field unrelated to clinical psychology. The Romanian version consists of the plural form of the noun *dulcegărie*, a unit created through derivation, its root *dulce* having its origin in the Latin *dulcis*, and the plural adjective *nesincere*, a negative prefixation of the adjective *sincer*, from French *sincère*, and Latin *sincerus*. In this case, the translator encountered a term based on a visual metaphor, and rephrased it in a way to retain the meaning and allow the term to sound natural in the target language.

With regard to the statistical data of the translation techniques used in rendering “TA Today” terminology, the most prominently used one is transposition, the second one is equivalence, and the third one is half-calque. Other, less productive techniques are literal translation, borrowing, and expansion. The least used technique was modulation, which is understandable due to the fact that it is not recommended in specialized translation.

Conclusion

Some points that we believe should be taken into consideration when translating clinical psychology terminology are that, *firstly*, one should always double-check meanings of terms, given that frequently online glossaries or other sources can contain mistakes, especially if they are not compiled by specialists. Even the most minor error or even ambiguity can lead to various consequences for the translator’s client, and consequently, can tarnish the reputation of the translator. When researching, a translator could find appropriate contexts for the terms in specialized literature, or at even methodological materials, which are more accessible for non-specialists and can clear up the meaning and usage of the term. *Secondly*, a translator should make sure the clinical psychology terminology he uses is consistent throughout the text, is not omitted or too ambiguous, and of course, that the appropriate technique is used to render it. Thus, we imply that a translator needs linguistic, terminological and translation knowledge and finely attuned research skills, so as to produce accurate translations.

References:

1. SAGER, J.C., *A Practical Course in Terminology Processing*, Amsterdam/Philadelphia: John Benjamins, 1990, 264 p.
2. CABRÉ, M.T., *Terminology: Theory, Methods and Applications*, Amsterdam/Philadelphia: John Benjamins, 1999, 247 p.
3. SPENCELEY, D., *Introduction to Transactional Analysis*, 2016, 23 p.
<http://www.ta-psychotherapy.co.uk/pdf/101.pdf> (accessed February 21, 2022)
4. STEWART, I., VANN, J., *TA Today: A New Introduction to Transactional Analysis*, Nottingham and Chapel Hill: Lifespace Publishing, 1987, 341 p.
5. Stewart, I., Vann, J., *AT astăzi: o nouă introducere în analiza tranzacțională*, trans. Constantin Chevereșan, Luminița Chevereșan, Timisoara: Mirton, 2004, 240 p.
6. VINAY, J.-P. and DARBELNET, J., *Stylistique comparée du français et de l’anglais, Comparative Stylistics of French and English, A Methodology for Translation*, translated and edited by Juan C. Sager and M.-J. Hamel, Benjamins Translation Library, vol. 11, Amsterdam/Philadelphia, John Benjamins, 1958, 358p.
7. NEWMARK, P., *A Textbook of Translation*, Hertfordshire: Prentice Hall, 1988, 292 p.
8. <http://www.oxforddictionaries.com> (accessed February 22, 2022)